

TECHNOLOGY FOR THE EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH PLAY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10218807>

Annotation. Preschool education is an educational organization that has an important responsibility for raising children as a mature developed person and comprehensively developing the young generation of knowledge and values that determine the whole future of the child. The game is the main activity of children of preschool age, through which the child is formed as a person.

Keywords: game activist, physical development, preschool age, mental, moral, didactic games, plot games, method, rule, action, action games, upbringing, psychic progress.

Play is a process that shapes the child's attitude to the outside world as an educational, labor activity. The game is of great importance in the physical development of the child, in the educational work of the preschool organization, in the mental, moral, labor and aesthetic education of the child. The implementation of each process of activity through play from educators in a phased educational system in each preschool educational organization is an activity aimed at educators to comprehensively know the surrounding life and different relationships of people in each age group. The play activity of a preschool child in terms of content changes every day depending on the situation, and therefore the child does not get tired of playing.

The importance of children in the process of play for the psychic development of active activity is that the different qualities and qualities of children in the process of play are not only inappropriate, but the ukar is re-strengthened. Therefore, from a psychological point of view, properly organized gaming activity grows the personality of the child in every possible way, and with it, the whole psychic processes are formed in the child. For children there is no limit to the content of the game, for preschool children the game activity is an important tool for their comprehensive development, and of course this type of activity is the main activity of UALR. In gaming activities, the child begins to be shaped as a subject of personality. The game has attracted the attention of famous scientists, educators for a long time. The role of the game process throughout the life of children in preschool age is considered incomparable since the activity of the game greatly contributes to the development of the child

not only physically, but also from the psychic side . Since the game is considered an important process in the upbringing of a child, education in organizations it is necessary that this activity is carried out at special times according to the agenda. That is, for gaming activities, Time is allocated before breakfast, after training, on a walk, before the time of departure in the evening. It is better to play didactic games with children at allotted times, deciphered table print games on the table , plot role-playing games. Game activity is the main type of activity of children with a particular developmental disability.

Since Game activity is always associated with changes in the external environment, their content is also a type of activity that is carried out as a result of the influence of external factors. Play activities are real life for children and can work well if the play process played to them is properly tallanized.L the link between the game changes as the child grows older. While the main form of education in small groups is considered a game , the role of education in training increases by the arrival of a large group.And when the preparatory group arrives, they awaken a passion for school education. But for children, the value of the game does not disappear, but its content changes. The game is the main means of raising the personality of a child.

The defect is of great importance in the functioning of the game, through speech the child's thoughts are exchanged. One of the main game tasks for the development of speech of preschool children is the enrichment of the child's words, the assimilation of concepts, the polysemy of the words used and their understanding of the semantic sphere . In the process of playing, speech activity is formed in the field and, of course, it forms a child's interest in his native language. There are different classifications to games, which according to these classifications are divided into:

Didactic games-teach children in the process of play about their lifestyle, nature, various phenomena. Deepens the child's cognitive skills. Didactic games pay great attention to the development of children's speech.

Educational games-children are taught education through play. In this, the game is taught knowledge, skills in a row.

Sports games are games that focus on keeping children healthy. Children are refreshed during the day through sports games.

Theater plays-in modern theater, the term “play” is carried out by the actor through various means of expression, namely, facial expressions, speech, gestures, various.

Musical games-children's interest in music increases through this type of game, and their ability to music is formed.

It is necessary to explain to the child the condition of each game only then will it be osson for them to master this activity. In competitive games, the game rule is defined by the children themselves in the game process. The rule is determined by the topic and rule of the games by adults. Rule games include; didactic Games, action games, musical games. The ability of an adult to choose a play for the purpose of educating children ensures that proper initiation into the UM is a successful implementation of the tasks set out in the "first step".

Games are a means of riveting and raising children. Psychologists consider the game to be a leading activity in the preschool age. Thanks to the game, the qualities that ensure the transition of children to the stage of high rebirth are provided, significant changes in its permission occur. In the game, the human side of the child's personality is formed in a hole that interacts with each other. Observing a child playing, it is possible to know his attitude to adults and comrades about his imagination in the mountain. In order to educate some quality in a person, it is necessary to develop other aspects of it. For example, rich games must be created from the content book to rivize the interest in the game of children, the ability to externalize for the development of children's creative games, in turn, a well-organized children's team will be needed. In the process of interpretation, playful technologies are used in the form of didactic playful lessons. In these lessons, the process of acquiring knowledge Awakens those brought up through the activities of the game. Through play activities in the life of the child, the following functions are performed:

- during the game, the person's access to communication is facilitated so that the communicative-communicative culture can take over;

- through the activity of the game, the interest in the reading of the individual, to mehant, is increased;

- it will be possible for the person to make his talent, interest, knowledge, self-esteem inappropriate;

- in the process of playing, the opportunity is created to master behavior corresponding to social norms, to eliminate shortcomings;

Game activity the game is intended to develop the culture of collective communication to the participants;

The following should be observed when lead a children's game:

1. Wrapping up the right relationship between play and labor;

2. In the game, the upbringing of children in physical and mental qualities inherent in the future family of Labor. Thus preschool education the role of the game in the pedagogical process of organizations is very large, and from the game it is widely useful in education and education in preschool education. The game is widely used in preschool organizations in the system of physical education of children

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